

MEASUREMENT OF SHRINKAGE FOR RESINS

By

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ABSTRACT:

The manufacturing of components made of advanced composite materials requires close control of the dimensions of the part. The curing of a component generally results in spatial variation in temperature, matrix volume fraction, degree of cure of the material at a certain instant of time. These spatial variations can cause distortions in configuration of the component. The variation in the dimensions of a part can result in warpage, out-of-dimensions, residual stresses, and poor surface finish, etc. Factors that affect the variation in the dimensions of the part can be the properties of the tool materials, the geometry of the tool, and, to a large extent the shrinkage of the resin. Information on the shrinkage of resin, up to now, has been mainly a single number, i.e. the difference between the volume of a certain mass of the material in the liquid state and that in the solid state. This single number gives an idea as to how much is the total shrinkage of the resin. However, it does not provide sufficient information for the modeling of the behavior of the material and/or structure during the curing process. It would be much more desirable if the whole history of the change in dimension of the material were available. This information would allow better models to be made and thus, permit better control on the processing parameters to control the dimensions of the part.

A Polymer Shrinkage and Modulus (PSM) Instrumentation has been developed at the Concordia Center for Composites. This instrumentation provides the capability to monitor the whole history of shrinkage of the resin from the liquid state to the solid state. This instrumentation has been developed using the ultrasonic technique. The shrinkage of water as a function of temperature is used as a calibration for the instrumentation. The histories of a few commonly used resins for composites have been measured using this instrumentation. This paper presents the principle of operation of the PSM Instrumentation and also the results of the history of shrinkage of a few resins.

INTRODUCTION:

Polymeric resins are known to shrink upon solidification. Chemical shrinkage can play an important role during processing. For epoxies, the volumetric shrinkage can be as much as 6 percent [1]. For polyesters and thermoplastics, the chemical shrinkage can be much higher.

Shrinkage of the resin plays a significant role in the residual stresses that develop within a part and the out-of-dimensions of the part. This out-of-dimension is the cause of warpage, poor surface finish, etc. For the manufacture of high quality aircraft composite components, the control of surface finish for high quality automotive composite parts, the tight dimensional control of the fitting of a crown on top of a tooth, the understanding and control of the shrinkage of the resin is of paramount importance. The need to have dimensional control has been the subject of many recent investigations in the manufacture of advanced composites [2,3].

For the measurement of shrinkage of polymeric resins, there are a few techniques available. In the conventional method (for example, ASTM D6289) a certain mass of the resin is taken for consideration. The relative difference between the volume of this mass in the liquid form and in the solid form is taken to be the coefficient of shrinkage. This coefficient of volumetric shrinkage is useful to provide a total shrinkage of the material. However it does not provide information on the history of the development of shrinkage during the solidification process.

A few designs for the monitoring of the history of shrinkage have been developed. Kinkelaar and Lee [4] developed a dilatometer for the measurement of shrinkage of low-shrink unsaturated polyester resins. This system places the resin to be examined inside a plastic pouch that in turn is placed between two metallic plates. The assembly is then placed inside an oil bath with controlled temperature. A metal arm (plunger) in contact with the metal plate moves up and down depending on the expansion or contraction of the sample. Either a weight or pressure is used to keep this arm in contact with the metal plate. The system was used to monitor the development of volumetric expansion or shrinkage of a few resins systems consisting of unsaturated polyesters and low profile additive. Russell et al [5] used a PVT (Pressure Volume Temperature) apparatus for the measurement of volumetric shrinkage of epoxy resins. The two designs mentioned seem to have the ability to measure the shrinkage of thermoset resins during cure. However these designs are complex. The design by Kinkelaar and Lee requires the draining of air from the plastic pouch and elaborate work to ensure contact between the plunger and the metal plate. The PVT machine also requires a complex set up. It utilizes mercury to be in contact with the specimen. It also requires at least 10 MPa (1450 psi) for its operation. The machine requires a good amount of space and can be quite noisy in operation.

ULTRASONIC INSTRUMENTATION:

A new instrumentation for the measurement of the history of shrinkage of polymeric resins (mainly thermosets) has been developed using ultrasonic techniques. This is called the PSM (Polymer Shrinkage Modulus) system [6]. Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of this instrumentation. In this instrumentation, the liquid sample is placed at the bottom of a container. The container is made of special ceramic material with very

low coefficient of thermal expansion. The expansion coefficient of the container is taken into consideration for the treatment of the signal for the determination of the shrinkage of the sample. On top of the sample is a couplant that does not react with the sample during the duration of the test. Immersed in the couplant is the ultrasonic sensor. The whole system of sensor, couplant, sample and container are immersed in a bath of controlled temperature. The temperature of the couplant is measured using a thermocouple.

This system measures the time of travel of ultrasonic signals from the surface of the sensor to the interface between the couplant and the sample. The product of this time and the velocity of travel of the ultrasonic waves in the couplant is the distance traveled, which is related to the height of the column of liquid or solid. The effect of the temperature on the velocity of travel of the ultrasonic signal in the couplant is calibrated and taken into consideration.

The position of the interface is used to determine the height of the column of material of the sample. This column height is converted to the volumetric shrinkage, assuming that the cross section area of the column remains constant. This assumption can be checked by observing whether the sample separates from the wall of the container either during or after the test.

The system is very simple to set up and to operate. The sample is subject to atmospheric pressure.

CALIBRATION OF THE INSTRUMENTATION:

In order to check the accuracy of the instrumentation, the shrinkage of a substance with known shrinkage characteristics, water was used as a check. Shrinkage of distilled water was determined by Ref [7]. In this experiment, 100 g of distilled water was used as the sample. The change in volume of this mass as the temperature changes from 26°C to 84 °C was measured using the PSM machine. Density was calculated by dividing the mass by the volume. Figure 2 shows the density results. Over this temperature range, the density of water decreases from about 1000 kg/m³ to about 970 kg/m³. The percent error for these results is less than 1%. The shrinkage results are shown in Figure 3. Over this temperature ranges, water shrinks about 3%. The ultrasonic results overestimates the shrinkage at low temperature and underestimates the shrinkage at higher temperature. This is thought of as due to the accuracy of the temperature measurement which is being improved.

SHRINKAGE HISTORY OF AN EPOXY AND A POLYESTER RESIN:

DOW DER. 324 Epoxy and TETA system:

For the first example, a resin system consisting of Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol A and TetraEthyleneTriAmine were used. 100 g of Dow DER. 324 and 12 g of TETA hardener were mixed using a blender for 10 minutes. Immediately before mixing, “ZERO” time was set. The oil bath temperature was set at 40° C. About 20 mls of the mixture were

poured into a beaker. The mass of the sample was recorded. The beaker was placed inside the PSM system. Ultrasonic signals were recorded over the duration of shrinkage of the sample. The contact between the sample and the wall of the container was examined for separation and no separation was observed.

The plot for the volumetric shrinkage versus process time for this material system is shown in Figure 4. This figure shows that it takes about 35 minutes before volume shrinkage begins to occur. This period of induction can be due to the effect of different ingredients inside the resin such as retarder or simply the time required for reaction to accelerate. The temperature shown in the figure is the temperature of the couplant. The temperature in the surrounding bath was maintained at 40°C. The increase in temperature of the couplant was due to the exothermic reaction of the resin. Volumetric shrinkage corresponds to an increase in temperature of the couplant. Most of the shrinkage takes within about 40 minutes. The rate of this shrinkage certainly depends on the temperature of the sample. Independent measurement of the total amount of volumetric shrinkage using conventional method (measurement of difference between volumes of liquid and solid of the same mass) shows a total shrinkage of 5.75%. This compares well with the data in Figure 4.

Unsaturated polyester system:

100 g of unsaturated polyester resin (AOC T580-63) was mixed with 1.5 g of Pulcat promoter. This was placed inside the PSM system for measurement. For this system, the temperature was varied from room temperature to 65°C. in order to overcome the effect of the inhibitor present in the resin. The temperature profile and the variation of the volumetric shrinkage is shown in Figure 5. The results show that the volumetric shrinkage goes up to 8%.

Figure 5 shows that initially when the sample is heated from room temperature (26 °C) to 70 °C, some expansion of the material occurs. This is reflected in the negative volume shrinkage in the curve. During the temperature hold at 70 °C, shrinkage slowly takes place. The fluctuations in the curve are due to the uncertainty in interpreting the ultrasonic signals. These fluctuations therefore should not be taken to have physical meaning. Shrinkage seems to have taken its completion after about 200 minutes into the test while the temperature was held at 70 °C. Increasing the temperature further results in some expansion of the material, which is exhibited by some drop in the shrinkage.

DISCUSSION:

The history of shrinkage depends on the temperature history of the sample. In the above examples, increase in temperature results in some form of expansion of the material. The effect of shrinkage may be separated from the expansion by holding the temperature constant. For this condition of constant temperature, the rate of shrinkage can be obtained using the slope of the curve of shrinkage versus time. This slope depends on the composition of the resin, such as the amount of catalysts, inhibitors, promoters etc.

The results obtained from the PSM system correlates well with the conventional measurement method (for the total amount of shrinkage). This system is very simple to set up and to operate. The system does not require any pressurization. Results shown in [4] indicated that there is no difference between volumetric shrinkage of polyester resins for two pressures of 100 psi and 200 psi. For many operations such as Resin Transfer Molding and Hand-Lay-Up, the pressure is not high and the results obtained at atmospheric pressure may be applicable to these manufacturing operations. The PSM system therefore can provide a simple, rigorous and accurate method for the characterization of shrinkage of many reactive resin systems. The shrinkage results may also be used to correlate with other measurements such as DSC to study the correlation between shrinkage and other phenomena such as gelling and degree of cure.

REFERENCES:

1. Yates B., McCalla B.A., Phillips L.N., Kingston-Lee D.M., and Rogers K.F., J. Materials Science, 1979, 14, p. 1207.
2. Koteswara M.P. and Raghavan J. "Process induced warpage in autoclave-cured composite laminates", Proc. CANCOM 2001, ed. S.V. Hoa, A. Johnston and J. Denault, Technomic, 2001, p.147.
3. Albert C., Ferlund G. and Poursartip A. "The effect of part design and process parameters on spring-in of angled composite parts", *ibid*, p. 155.
4. Kinkelaar M. and Lee L.J. "Development of a dilatometer and its application to low-shrink unsaturated polyester resins", J. of Applied Polymer Science, Vol. 45, 37-50, 1992.
5. Russell J.D., Madhukar M.S., Genidy M.S., and Lee A.Y. "A new method to reduce cure-induced stresses in thermoset polymer composites, Part III: Correlating stress history to viscosity, degree of cure, and cure shrinkage", J. Composite Materials, Vol. 34, No. 22, 2000, pp. 1926-1947.
6. Hoa S.V. and Ouellette P. "System for measuring shrinkage behavior and modulus change during cure of a liquid resin sample", Patent pending.
7. Landolt-Bomstein, Numerical Data and Functional Relationships in Science and Technology, New Series, Group II: Atomic and Molecular Physics, Vol. 5, Molecular Acoustics, Hellwege, K.-H and Hellwege A.M. Eds., Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1967.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the PSM machine.

SHRINKAGE OF WATER

Figure 2: Change in density of water over temperature change

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Figure 3: Shrinkage of water over a temperature range.

Figure 4: Volumetric Shrinkage curve for DOW DER 324 epoxy resin.

**AOC T-580 POLYESTER WITH PULCAT A PROMOTER
(IN AN OIL BATH)**

Figure 5: Volumetric shrinkage curve for unsaturated polyester resin.